

FORMATION OF INDEPENDENT CREATIVE WORK ACTIVITIES IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: *In the article the student realizes, perceives, perceives, imagines and remembers the correctness, accuracy, authenticity, validity or relevance of the events and phenomena that he reflects, perceives, assumes, assumes in the process of independent thinking. generalize, understand the internal, complex connections, relationships, properties, characteristics and mechanisms between things and events, the student to predict the emergence, development and consequences of natural and social phenomena and events based on certain laws, laws and regulations the formation of abilities, the importance of independent thinking in the rational, efficient organization of the student's cognitive and practical activities are analyzed in detail.*

Key words: student, education, system, process, creation, research, thinking, perception, imagination, understanding, hypothesis, conclusion, formation.

In the process of education, great attention is paid to the fact that they do not discriminate against any stratum of society, to develop personnel who can think independently and creatively. One of the urgent tasks is to develop the aptitude, abilities, knowledge and skills of young people, to teach general subjects for them to take up their chosen professions, to effectively organize their independent and creative work, to provide this process with new teaching materials.

We need specialists with well-developed thinking and independent thinking in various fields. It is a modern requirement that the study of independent thinking of students should be a priority in the educational process. Throughout a child's life, independent thinking at all stages of education should remain a basic requirement. Thinking or reasoning is the highest form of student mental activity, intellectual intelligence, rhythm of behavior, conscious behavior. Independent thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social environment and reality, as well as the main condition for the rational, efficient implementation of a wide range of intellectual activities of the student. In the realization of independent thinking, the

student develops ideas, reflections, ideas, hypotheses, goals, etc., and they are expressed in the mind of the person as concepts, judgments, conclusions. Independent thinking manifests itself in close connection with language and speech, and they are continuously interdependent. For the same reason, the student is radically different from the beings in existence due to his independent thinking (communication), speech, and conscious behavior.

Typically, thinking is divided into several types depending on the degree of generalization of reality, the nature of the problem-solving tool, the novelty of the object for the student and its motivation for activity [1]. When analyzing independent thinking as a mental activity, it involves the solution of problems and tasks by the student, observed in their conditions, essence, structure, forms and possibilities of understanding and comprehension of the individual. Problem, problem, task solving (solving, execution) is considered in connection with the student's needs, interests, inclinations, motivations, mental abilities, talents, potentials, accepting the requirements of the problem, making personal decisions, searching for solutions, form a solid foundation for research and thinking. In independent and creative thinking activities, the management of the problem-solving process, the student's emotions, inner experiences, emergencies, objective conditions are of special importance for him in the perception of existence.

In social life in the system of higher education, in the practice of production, the rhythm of interpersonal (objective, subjective) relations, connections, the result of joint mental and physical labor occurs as a complex of non-standard thinking. Qualities of independent thinking in the student community include criticism and self-criticism, assessment and self-assessment, review and self-monitoring, management and self-governance, self-development, self-expression, self-command, group reflection and personal observation formed [2].

Human perception of a person, i.e., determining the mental state of a stranger, guessing him, collecting materials about the most necessary signs and symptoms, is also a product of creative thinking. This complex stage-by-stage process of cognition requires volitional effort, mental seriousness, conscious attitude, a stable situation, favorable conditions, through the direct influence of which a certain decision is made.

Creative works, discoveries, inventions, inventive proposals are also the product of creative thinking, and its tasks include scientific assumptions, ideas, glorious goals, lofty noble intentions of practical and theoretical significance [3].

Student thinking activity is social in nature. During the period of social and historical development of thinking, there was a need to exchange ideas and share experiences, first in search of food for food, and then in the creation and use of tools of labor. As a result of human interaction, interaction, and communication, the ability to express opinions and speak has begun to emerge. Thanks to the speech, the consistency, logic, systematization of the products of thinking has emerged, which has the opportunity to leave as a traditional legacy for future generations. Had the systematized experience, knowledge, skills and abilities accumulated by mankind not been left behind, human thinking would not have been able to achieve such great achievements in the fields of science, technology and culture [4, 5, 6].

In the activity of independent thinking, the student determines the accuracy, precision, authenticity, truthfulness of the things and events that he reflects, perceives, perceives, imagines, remembers, or whether they fall into reality (appropriate) and do not understand. Judgments, concepts, conclusions, hypotheses (assumptions) formed in the process of knowing existence determine whether decisions are true or not. The student, through independent thinking, indirectly or indirectly reflects the reality, generalizes, understands the internal, complex connections, relationships, properties, features and mechanisms between things and events. Consequently, the student has the opportunity to predict the occurrence, course, development of natural and social phenomena and events, as well as their consequences, based on certain laws, laws and regulations. The importance of independent thinking is especially important in the rational, efficient organization of cognitive and practical activities of modern students.

Independent thinking in a student begins with the emergence of a problematic situation, but the emergence of this situation, the solution does not end there [7]. The tendency of the student to know, involuntary behavior does not shine until the problem situation, it occurs vaguely, then a problem situation in need of a solution is created in this sense, and finally its solution is found, but the post-problem stage of cognition continues involuntarily in its direction [8].

In the student's learning activity there is a tightly interconnected chain of thinking: independent thinking, problem, issue (assignment).

Student independent thinking can be structured in the following stages.

1. In the activity of independent thinking, first of all, the problem (task) that needs to be solved should be identified by the student. If there is no

issue or problem in front of him, then he does not even think about anything. This means that the student is not confronted with any problem, the easier and more complete the information he has to solve, the easier it will be for him to find a way and means to do it wisely. To do this, students must first understand the content of the issue to a certain extent, check its conditions, determine what is known and what is unknown. Only in this way will they not be in a hurry and will be able to search for the condition without hesitation (task), analyze it with their minds, and solve it correctly.

2. Strive to apply all the knowledge (rules, factors, laws, properties, attributes, important features, relationships, connections, etc.) that is most necessary to solve a problem or issue. To do this, the process of transfer to a new environment, the object, using the situations encountered in the personal experience of the student, effective methods.

3. Hypothesis (hypothesis) related to the problem or problem is put forward, the stages are analyzed, the solution is considered, various options and variations, invariants are expressed, which are divided into the most effective signs, symbols, etc. as a result of mutual comparison.

4. It is necessary to test the hypothesis of the problem with the help of the results of certain criteria. To examine it, the cases of mutual similarity are compared in spiritual, formal, structural terms. In this case, the materials of creative imagination are used in detail, that is, to make creative plans, to create generalized images, to visualize the results, to understand the hypothetical relationships. To ensure that it is valid, a system of mental behaviors is applied and the intention to make some changes is clarified. The hypothesis is analyzed and synthesized using logical methods, its important features are distinguished, and quick judgments and conclusions are made on its correctness and validity.

5. If it is determined that the hypothesis put forward to solve the problem theoretically is correct or incorrect, it is squeezed out of the object of reasoning and new hypotheses, ideas are found. The new practical hypothesis idea is tested several times and then it is recommended to try it to put it into practice. Most of the considerations are analyzed in the solution of constructive technical problems, inventions, inventions, rationalizations, introduction of technological devices, various models, options, drugs, technological maps, etc. the fit is selected and the head-scratching on it is continued.

6. To solve a problem or issue, to solve it, to create confidence and satisfaction in the correctness of the results obtained, the student completes the independent thinking behavior by examining it. It is these mental

operations, after the forms of reflection, that the problem (task) is found to be completely solved, and thinking about it is relatively stopped.

The student's independent thinking can consist of the following stages:

1. The emergence of the problem in the field of student perception.
2. Understanding of the essence of the problem, problem, assignment by the student.
3. The emergence of similar data or images.
4. Decrease in imagination and memory materials, continuous birth of assumptions.
5. Step-by-step verification of assumptions or confirmation of their validity.
6. The emergence and improvement of new assumptions.
7. Secondary test of assumptions (second confirmation)
8. Problem, task, problem solving (Solution).
9. Continuation of involuntary mental behavior (relative duration of thoughts), etc.

In order to teach students to think independently, it is advisable to pay attention to the following, taking into account the spiritual, formal, structural aspects of the problem:

- One of the options of questions, which are expressed after the analysis of the problems, issues, assignments, connections between them, connections, relationships, the questions of which are not specified, are indicated in parentheses;

- Problems, issues, tasks, missing information for their solution (execution, solution) remain in parentheses;

- problem, issue, assignment with excess information, details;

- Problems, issues, tasks that can be solved, solved, performed in several ways, methods, step by step, where various issues (problems, tasks) are given, with the most convenient, simple, most economical, efficient way of solving as hidden as possible the transition of problems from one mode of thinking to another, from a simpler sentence to a more complex one, from one conclusion to its particular appearances and forms, will be aimed at shaping the student's mental ability;

- Problems, issues, tasks, the content and essence of which change, they also focus on the formation of mental abilities, consisting of the transition from one reinforced mental behavior to another, that is, they are taught to use them in the process of moving to a new situation;

- Problems, issues, tasks aimed at proving, discovering, discovering, with the help of which logical thinking improves mental abilities, such as proving internal relations, understanding the laws;

- Independent thinking, logical reasoning, problems, assignments, issues, no special knowledge is required to solve them, but it requires a certain level of creativity, appeal to life, the ability to think logically, some of which are mathematical. , others are referenced only in the form of logical puzzles.

Independent thinking, with its effectiveness, relevance, universality, professional training leads students to mastery, provides a solid foundation for understanding society and natural phenomena.

Independence of thinking means that the student is able to set a clear goal, new tasks on his own initiative, to make practical and theoretical, characteristic hypotheses (roughly, hypotheses) on them, to imagine the expected result, to solve the problem without anyone's help or guidance. due to his mental research, it is possible to understand the mental ability to find different ways, methods, means and solve them independently [9].

The independence of thought is manifested in the diligence, perseverance, and critique of the mind. The initiative of the mind means that the student sets a clear goal, a clear task for the new problem, to complete all this, to personally look for ways and means to find a solution, to make mental efforts, to introduce additional signs and symptoms. is held. The perseverance of the mind is expressed in the rapid solution of tasks, in the precise application of new methods and means in solving them, in the liberation from old ways, and in other mental processes.

The criticality of the mind is important in being able to examine one's own and others' opinions, whether these opinions are true or not, and to be able to evaluate the opinions, discussions, and problematic situations that have arisen. Such critique is called objective critique if it is based on a certain criterion for the correct disclosure of the essence of the problem to a reasonable, important character. A situation in which a student's critical thinking shifts to subjective (personal) errors in general to subjectivism is called subjective criticality. It is safe to say that if the critical thinking in the student's thinking is carried out rationally, fairly, efficiently, then both mental and moral qualities (qualities) that are important for the person will emerge.

The independence of a student's thinking is inextricably linked to his or her productivity. If a student for a certain period of time has made valuable and new ideas, ideas, recommendations for a particular field, and solved theoretical and practical tasks, such a person's thinking is called productive. serves as a criterion. Even when the student thinks of simple things, he is not

limited to their external signs, but seeks to reveal the essence of events, trying to create a general social law from the realities of ordinary life. Undoubtedly, the student's independent thinking has untapped and untapped potential, the full discovery of which serves the purpose of accelerating the development of science and technology. Any organization, innovation is the product of development-human intelligence, so the development of science and technology in many respects depends on the independent thinking of the specialist. Student maturity consists of physical, moral and mental stages, in which his independent thinking takes the lead, a priority. Although today's students easily reach the level of physical and moral perfection, but the achievement of mental maturity can be achieved gradually, thanks to the patterns of nervous system tension, mental tension, emotional seriousness, stable willpower, continuous activity, devotion. It is expedient to form in students independent thinking, creative research, methods of intellectual activity in order to acquire the spirituality and values created by our ancestors, as well as to ensure their future development.

At present, the form of organization of teaching in higher education does not fully form the ability to acquire and learn independently. This situation has a negative impact on the development of an independent and free-thinking person. There is also very little research on the development and activation of independent work and creative activity of young people.

The development of methods for the effective organization and conduct of independent work in higher education, the use of active methods aimed at the development of creative activities of students remains a requirement of the times.

In conclusion, the rapid development of science and technology, the widespread introduction of modern information and communication systems, the rapid renewal of knowledge in various fields, the daily changes in techniques and technologies allow for independent learning, the creation and implementation of electronic textbooks. requires the development of methodologies. The content of e-textbooks created in general professional subjects should be focused on the development of creative abilities of students, provide opportunities for independent learning, the formation of skills to search for new knowledge. Based on the above details and analysis, scientific research on the above-mentioned problems indicates that it is an urgent task today.

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